

Perceptions of Learners on Reading Enhancement during Catch-Up Fridays

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Abstract

DepEd issued a memorandum requiring all public schools from Grades 1 to 12 and all community learning centers to implement Catch-up Fridays. Catch-up Fridays is a learning mechanism intended to strengthen the foundational, social, and other relevant skills necessary to actualize the intent of the basic education curriculum that shall be implemented every Friday until the end of the school year 2023–2024. This study aims to assess the reception of the Reading Enhancement by determining the perceptions and experiences of the learners. To gain a rich and in-depth understanding of how the learners perceive the implementation of RE, a focus group with semi-structured interviews was conducted. When the learners were asked how they felt about RE in general, they mostly claimed that they were enjoying the activities. The innovative approaches for conducting classes were applauded by the learners, too. However, some learners also expressed their disapproval. They declared that they would rather have regular classes over RE. When the learners were asked whether they liked or disliked having the RE program each Friday, most showed thumbs-downs. However, when the learners were asked about their expectations, they were positive that the programs on Catch-up Fridays would be beneficial to them after all. Thus, the teachers are advised to innovate and strategize beyond the recommendations of the DepEd order and memorandum. Conclusively, all stakeholders of the basic education in the nation must work together for the welfare and benefits of the learners.

Keywords: Catch-Up Fridays, DepEd Catch-Up Fridays, perceptions on reading enhancement, Reading Enhancement, Reading Enhancement on Catch-Up Fridays

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1. Introduction

On the 10th day of the month of January in the year 2024, the Department of Education (DepEd), the primary government agency mandated to govern the basic education in the Republic of the Philippines, issued a memorandum requiring all public schools from Grade 1 to 12 (elementary and secondary) and all community learning centers to implement the Catch-up Fridays. Catch-up Fridays is a learning mechanism intended to strengthen the foundational, social, and other relevant skills necessary to actualize the intent of the basic education curriculum that shall be implemented on every Friday starting from the 12th day of January 2024 until the end of the school year 2023–2024 (DepEd Memorandum No. 001, s. 2024).

One of the main features of the Catch-up Fridays, in fact the grandest, taking up the schedule for the first half of the day with a 140-minute time allotment, is the operationalization of the National Reading Program (NRP), a subprogram of the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP). The NRP is both a core reading curriculum and a supplementary initiative aimed at improving literacy standards through enhancement, intervention, and remediation that harmonizes all reading programs implemented in the DepEd schools (DepEd Order no. 013, s. 2023).

Being a secondary school institution of DepEd, the Jose Lim Ho National High School in Calabayan, Ozamiz City, in compliance with the mandates of the agency, implemented Catch-up Fridays in its campus involving the Grade 7 up to the Grade 10 (junior high school) and the Grade 11 and Grade 12 (senior high school) levels. With regard to operationalizing the NRP, two reading groups were determined in the school, namely, the Reading Intervention (RI) and the Reading Enhancement (RE) groups. The first group has been intended for the learners who were identified to have lower reading comprehension skills while the latter has been intended for the learners who were identified to have average to advanced reading comprehension skills.

This study aims to assess the reception of the RE by the learners by determining the perceptions and experiences of the Grade 11 learners at the Jose Lim Ho National High School. While the Catch-up Fridays has been running for more than two months, there has been a dearth of studies conducted and published in its relevance. Despite there are news features published by the Philippine Information Agency and the Philippine News Agency—both owned by the Philippine government, no official or formal study regarding the perceptions of the learners is available at hand. Moreover, this undertaking intends to shed light on the learners' reception of RE during the Catch-up Fridays for the school administrators, teachers, policy- and decision-makers to devise strategies and impactful decisions on the program for the benefit of the learners.

2. Literature Review

As claimed by a school teacher in a news article, the Catch-up Fridays came as a challenge for both teachers and learners (Bermudez, 2024) despite having a good initial

impression as having both teachers and learners “happy and engaged,” as claimed by the DepEd’s Curriculum and Teaching Strand (Bacelonia, 2024). In consistency with the guides and strategies suggested in DepEd Order no. 013, s. 2023, the learner experience of the Catch-up Fridays would be tailored to their needs and integrative with other various learning areas, particularly in health, values education and peace education.

Elladora & Dioso (2023) contend in their paper that language proficiency must go hand-in-hand with literary competence. Literary competence involves various abilities and understandings crucial for comprehending texts. Learners need competencies such as contextual understanding, reading strategies, literary analysis, and textual knowledge to develop it. Moreover, in the digital era, digital literacy skills are essential for effectively engaging with and evaluating digital texts, adding a new dimension to literary competence. It is, therefore, reasonable that teachers must employ various strategies beyond the suggestions provided by the DepEd order and memorandum to cater to the complex aspects of literary competence should they aim to enhance the reading skills of the learners.

Aside from employing varied approaches and strategies, it is also highly proposed by Francia (2022) that the reading materials must be interactive, supportive of independent learning and simple in nature for them to become appealing to the learners. Hence, motivated learners learn better.

Moreover, the Reading Enhancement and Assessment Plan (REAP) has been proposed by Sor & Caraig (2021) to monitor and enhance the reading level of the learners and to develop intervention programs that will cater to their needs. Furthermore, to enhance the learners’ reading comprehension skills, it is suggested to continually provide word recognition, oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension activities.

Lastly to add, a study on intensive reading interventions on English learners with learning disabilities in the United States suggests that it is necessary to have strengthened intensive reading interventions in addition to school-wide programs to enhance reading outcomes, for the reason that even after intervention, the learners demonstrate low- and below-average reading performance (Williams & Vaughn, 2019). With regard to the RE activity on Catch-up Fridays, intensive reading should be employed too.

While the pieces of local and international literature discussed above propose specific strategies and present robust rationale for reading enhancement, there is a scant availability of studies focusing on the perceptions and experiences of the learners on such programs and activities. Thus, the findings of this study shall add insights and serve as a bridge over the identified gaps to help policy- and decision-makers design and implement mechanisms for the benefits of the learners in general.

3. Methodology

To gain a rich and in-depth understanding of how the learners perceive the implementation of Reading Enhancement, a focus group with semi-structured interviews was conducted on the Grade 11 learners from the two RE groups during the Catch-up Fridays at the Jose Lim Ho National High School. The focus group participants were selected

randomly and based on availability. The sample consisted of nine males and twelve females. Even though the sample composition had varied academic achievement statuses and varied learning strands, these learners were all identified as average to advanced readers.

The Grade 11 learners in the school were divided into three groups, one for the RI and two for the RE. Those learners identified as having challenges and assessed below average in reading were sent to the RI group, while those who were identified as average and above average readers were sent to the two RE groups. For the RE groups, the learners were sorted alphabetically based on their surnames. The first half went to the first group and the second half went to the other. This means that learners from various learning strands were grouped together regardless of sex and academic status.

The participants to be studied were specifically asked how they felt about the Catch-up Fridays, particularly for the RE activities. Also, they were asked to say anything whether good or bad, about what they liked or disliked, and asked to explain the reasons behind their responses. Also, additionally, they were asked what their expectations of and suggestions for the weekly program.

The responses were manually recorded, coded, and then analyzed for themes.

3.1. Scope and Limitation

The study focused only on the RE program, thus, RI and other components of the Catch-up Fridays were not covered. Additionally, the participants were only Grade 11 in the RE program and did not include Grade 11 in RI and so as the other grade levels. Additionally, further, the study was conducted exclusively in the school, which means, no community learning center, private and other schools were involved.

Furthermore, the interviews were conducted by the researchers who were teachers at the school, thus, some bias from both the interviewer's and the participants' side might have arisen and had been overlooked. Furthermore, still, the study was conducted only after two months from the actual implementation of the Catch-up Fridays in the school.

3.2. Ethical Consideration

Consent and permissions from the school administrators, teaching staff, and learners were secured before commencing the formal data gathering. Also, the participants were orally asked or interviewed first before they had been informed that the data they would provide would be used in a formal research. This had been done to minimize biases or avoid, specifically, observer-expectancy and Hawthorne effects (Tenny et al., 2022). Afterward, the responses were transcribed and shown to the participating individuals for affirmation and it was stated in the assent that they could withdraw or opt not to include their responses for the study and that there would be no effect or any impact on their academic grades or any scholastic aspect whatever action they would take regarding this very study. Lastly, there was no personal identifying information of the individual participant was kept and used in the study.

4. Results and Discussion

The main purpose of this study has been to gain insights about the Reading Enhancement program in the Catch-up Fridays from the learners' perspective. After prudent research undertaking about the topic, the researchers had gathered the following findings which are presented herein. Then it was found out that the learners have varied takes on the RE program, some exclaimed their positive perceptions while some expressed their negative takes. Hence, responses from the interviews included general and specific aspects of the program.

When the learners were asked how they felt about RE in general, they mostly claimed that they were enjoying the activities. The learners claimed that they were excited since they were grouped with the other learners from different learning strands, consequently, new faces and a different class setting for them.

The various, new approaches for conducting classes were applauded by the learners, too. RE classes were tackled differently compared to the traditional classroom setting. Various strategies were implemented by the teachers in RE classes, which are: Drop Everything and Read, Teacher Read-Aloud, Book Talk, Choral Reading, Partner Reading, and Red-a-thon, combined with assorted activities for motivation and interactivity, such as games and role-plays, preventing monotony in the class.

However, some learners expressed their disapproval, too. They declared that they would rather have regular classes over RE. Some claimed that Catch-up Fridays defeats its own purpose, which is to improve learning gains and recover learning losses, since regular classes are condensed to four days in week. Some even reasoned out that they disliked the group activities since their groupmates were no longer the faces that they used to work and learn with. Some even argued that reading should not be shoved on everyone since not everyone likes reading, they even proposed to have various leisurely activities for the learners to choose from such as dancing, singing, poetry, drama, art, cooking and others.

Moreover, two teacher groups, namely, the Alliance of Concerned Teachers (ACT) and the Teachers' Dignity Coalition (TDC), reported that the learners are disengaged in the Catch-up Fridays activities hence they skip school on Fridays (Chi, 2024).

Overall, when the learners were asked whether they like or dislike having the RE program each Friday, in general, through the rest of the school year, most of them showed their thumbs-downs. This is somehow consistent with report of the Asian Affairs (2024) on January 12th that learners were critical of the Catch-up Fridays claiming that this exacerbates workload and stress, as the learners feel pressured to make up for missed subjects during the week, leading to diminished free time and flexibility, particularly amidst the pandemic, and express boredom and frustration due to the perceived repetitiveness and dullness of the program.

However, when the learners were asked about their expectations, they were positive that the programs on Catch-up Fridays would be beneficial to them after all. Though the learners expressed their boredom and dislike for the program, they were hopeful that the activities would change and that their proposed leisurely activities like dancing, singing, poetry, drama, art, cooking and the like would be incorporated in the program.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Despite the great intentions of the Catch-up Fridays program of DepEd, which are to strengthen the learners' learning in the disciplines, particularly in reading, values, and health, there has been a dichotomy of perceptions from the learners, teachers, and some concerned groups. Some learners take the program positively while some do not and some have high expectations while some have next to nothing new.

In light of the results obtained from this study, since DepEd is firm on its decision to instill the Catch-up Fridays and its components (Sevillano, 2024) and since Implementation of Catch-up Fridays is a binding nationwide memorandum (DepEd Memorandum No. 001, s. 2024), it is thus recommended that teachers must continue on implementing the program while devising strategies to make the activities more engaging and interesting for the learners.

The Reading Enhancement component of the Catch-up Fridays must be integrated with leisurely activities which the learners highly demand. Therefore, the teachers are advised to innovate and strategize beyond the recommendations of the DepEd order and memorandum by incorporating, for instance, a karaoke time which allows readers to enhance reading by singing out the lyrics, or a movie time to enhance the learners' ability to find context clues for difficult words by looking at the motion pictures and events in the movies, or perhaps, a cooking time which allows learners to read recipes and distinguish difficult words used in culinary arts.

The school heads, administrators, and head teachers are also recommended to conduct training and seminars for the teachers and devise strategies and mechanisms to improve the delivery of the activities of all the components of the Catch-up Fridays.

Conclusively, all stakeholders of the basic education in the whole nation must work together for the welfare and benefits of all the learners.

5.1. For Future Researches

Further studies are highly proposed to expand the understanding on the learners' perception of the Catch-up Fridays implemented by the Department of Education of the Republic of the Philippines, especially in the Reading Enhancement. It is recommended to expand the study beyond the delimited Grade 11 and include the Reading Intervention groups and so as the geographical context.

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Conflict of Interest

The researchers declare no conflict of interest regarding the conduct of this study and the publication of this research paper.

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